

THE IMPORTANT IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS IN INCREASING THE PHYSICAL ACTIVITY OF CHILDREN IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

Kudyarova Artikgul

Student of the Faculty of primary education of
The Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz

Abstract. It is known that increasing the physical activity of children in primary education serves as a foundation for their future physical performance. In this article, it is recommended that the pedagogical control and analysis of students' physical condition in lessons and extracurricular activities be based on a unified system of concepts, terms and measurement procedures.

Keywords: young generation, educational system, pedagogic science, physical activity, motor skills, mathematical analysis, pedagogical control.

INTRODUCTION

Without experimentally based data on the initial indicators of the physical capabilities of the growing body of children in the school education system, it is impossible to evaluate the results of targeted methods of pedagogical influence and build prospects for planning. It is known that any control tests begin with measurement and the need to know what indicators to measure and to choose the most informative indicators. An important part of this process is to be able to mathematically correctly process the results obtained during the pedagogical test. A modern physical education teacher of a general educational institution should master the methods of pedagogical control and analysis of students' physical condition during classes and extracurricular activities on selected types of children's sports.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of a unified scientific approach to the assessment of the physical capabilities and readiness of primary school students and the evaluation of comprehensive research results in the field of physical education, as well as the structure of the educational process in the school education system in accordance with the priorities set for public education by the state and tasks aimed at fundamentally revising the content, preventing negative manifestations of physical qualities in children at all subsequent stages of heterochronic development of abilities, and using sensitive and convenient age factors aimed at developing children's mobility to choose a type of sports skill.

In order to determine the physical fitness of children of primary school age, a number of tests from the state programs of "Health" school physical education and health tests were selected, and monitoring studies were conducted for the studied characteristics on quarterly basis.

RESULTS

During the pedagogical experiment, 24 physical education teachers working with children of primary school age took part in sociological research.

The contingent of physical education teachers working in the lower classes of the school education system showed that teachers with up to 5 years of work experience with this contingent of children - 37.4%, from 6 to 10 years old - 36.7% , 15.3% from 11 to 14 years old, 7.8% from 16 to 20 years old, 2.8% older than 20 years old work with teachers.,

57.4% have satisfactory conditions for conducting physical education classes and various physical education and sports activities, good conditions - 20.0%, conditions that meet the necessary requirements - 3.4% , physical education - health work with children - analyzes 17.8%.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

According to teachers, 28.7 percent of schools have complete sports

equipment, while the rest have only some of their elements. This allows us to conclude that there are no qualified sports and recreational activities with children of primary school age in the studied school institutions.

Responding to the urgent question of what should be done to improve the physical fitness of primary school students, the respondents unanimously emphasized the need for training by physical education specialists.

Due to their professional training and qualifications, teachers use various forms of physical exercises before classes, morning hygienic gymnastics, and physical education during classes to solve the problems of health direction. we hold national open games and various sports and recreational activities during the big breaks.

The evaluation of the competence of primary school teachers in conducting sports and health activities showed that 25.7% of them rated it as good, and 74.3% as satisfactory.

The opinion of parents was studied on the issue of increasing physical culture with elementary school students in school educational institutions.

The opinion of parents on the issue of improving the state of physical education and their age and quality composition aroused special interest. The monitoring of the results of personal data analysis showed that 36.8% of respondents are parents under 20 years old, 33.8% are 20-25 years old, 18.6% are 26-30 years old, and 10.8% are Over 30 years old.

According to the survey data, as a result of the analysis of the quality of parents' education, 8.8% have incomplete secondary education, 26.6% secondary education, 24.8% secondary special education, It was found that 39.8 percent have higher education.

CONCLUSIONS

Modernization in the field of school physical education of children of primary school age should be aimed at differentiating in detail the content of the

pedagogical process depending on the physical development, mobility and functional capabilities of this contingent of children.

REFERENCES

1. Learning methods in primary grades-Tashkent 2019
2. ЕРМАТОВА, Р. О. (2018). УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ВРЕМЕННЫМ УЧЕНИЕМ ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ С ОБУЧЕНИЕМ ИНВАЛИДЫ. *Наука среди нас*, (7), 85-88.
3. Ermatova, R. O. (2018). ADVANTAGES OF THE TECHNIQUE "WHAT/HOW/WHY OUTLINES" IN DEVELOPING PRODUCTIVE SKILLS OF THE MEDICAL STUDENTS. *Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук*, (6), 69-71.
4. Utegenova, S., & Rozumova, D. (2024). DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING TAX AUDIT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6).
5. Utegenova, S., & Mirzabaeva, U. (2024). TODAY'S IMPORTANCE AND PROSPECTS OF AUDIT ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 4(6), 93-95.
6. Utegenova, S., & Oralbaeva, F. (2024). O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotiga xorijiy investitsiyalar oqimini oshirishda mamlakatning investitsion muhiti jozibadorligini oshirish. *Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана*, 1(6), 131-134.
7. Khasanova, S., Akisheva, N., & Zholayeva, M. (2023). Methodological aspects of tax planning in the context of sustainable development. *Revista Gestão & Tecnologia*, 23(3), 286-298.
8. Маматқулов, Б. М., & Нематов, А. А. (2021). Ўзбекистон Республикаси аҳолиси орасида COVID-19 тарқалишининг хусусиятлари.

9. Abdullayeva, N. (2023). AHMAD YASSAWI SECT: THE ISSUE OF ZIKR AND THE STATUS OF ZAKIR. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 438-440.
10. Bazarov, S. (2024). JURNALIST VA BLOGERLAR NUTQI ETIKASI. *Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика*, 3(1), 36-39.
11. Norqulovich, S. H. (2023, October). NURILLO CHORINING BADIY ASARLARIDA MILLIY KOLORITGA XOS KO ‘RINISHLAR NUTQIY JIHATDAN IFODALANISHI. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 25-29).
12. Ziyodullayeva, M., & Muxtorova, M. (2024). ABDULLA QODIRIY HAYOTI VA IJODIGA AYRIM CHIZGILAR. *NRJ*, 1(3), 860-863.
13. Muxtorova, M. (2024). MAXTUMQULI SHE’RIYATIDA AYTISHUV: AN’ANA VA IZDOSHLIK. *NRJ*, 1(3), 254-257.
14. Tajenova, G., Turdiyeva, G., Qurbanov, A., & Isakov, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Архив научных исследований*, (14).
15. Janabay, I., Gulbahar, T., Gulayda, T., Alisher, Q., & Ilkhambek, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the republic of uzbekistan. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(8), 1684-1693.
16. Turdieva, G., Abishov, M., & Muratbaev, I. (2024). THE IMPACT OF CREDIT RISKS ON AN EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION IN THE FINANCIAL SERVICES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS. *NRJ*, 1(4), 215-225.
17. Beglenov, N., & Muratbaev, I. (2023). HOTEL SERVICES AS AN OBJECT OF STRATEGIC MARKETING ORIENTED TO THE

- CONSUMER. *Science and Education in Karakalpakstan*, 32(2), 175-177.
18. Xalmuratovich, B. S. (2024). JAHON AMALIYOTIDA AGROKLASTER TIZIMINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH VA YURITISH BO ‘YICHA TO ‘PLANGAN TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI. *Scientific Journal of Actuarial Finance and Accounting*, 4(04), 140-150.
19. Bayjanov, S. X., & Abishov, M. S. (2024). DEVELOPING THE ACTIVITY OF JOINT STOCK COMPANIES BY IMPROVING DIVIDEND POLICY. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 3(3), 94-97.
20. Sultanov, B., Nurimbetov, T., Bayjanov, S., Seyilbekov, B., & Durmanov, A. (2023, October). Trends in change and the current state of the effectiveness of land reclamation measures in agriculture. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2921, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
21. Байжанов, С. Х. (2023). ВНЕДРЕНИЕ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ В СЕЛЬСКОЕ ХОЗЯЙСТВО НОВОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(4), 51-53.
22. Омоновна, Е. Р. (2023). KLINIK ATAMALAR SHAKLLANTIRISHDA SUFFIKSATSIYA USULI VA TA ‘LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARI. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 9(3), 198-204.
23. Shodiyeva, G. (2024). O ‘ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILIDA SO ‘ZLARNI TURKUMLARGA AJRATISH MASALALARI. *Interpretation and researches*, (4 (26)).
24. qizi Tursunova, M. A., & qizi Shodieva, G. N. (2023). MAIN INFLUENTIAL FACTORS TO LANGUAGE LEARNING

PROCESS. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(3 SPECIAL), 1181-1183.

25. Aliyeva, N., & qizi Shodiyeva, G. N. (2023). Ingliz Tilida So ‘Z Turkumlari Tasnifi Masalalari Sharhi. *Scholar*, 1(13), 22-27.

26. Navruza, A. (2023). INGLIZ TILI MORFOLOGIYASIDA SOZ TURKUMLARINI ORGANISH ZARURIYATI. *ITALY" ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN THE FACE OF MODERN CHALLENGES"*, 14(1).